

Evaluation of machine learning techniques for Barrett's and Dysplasia discrimination of the Esophagus from *In Vivo* Optical Coherence Tomography Images

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ABSTRACT

Optical Coherence Tomography (EOCT) systems can acquire high-resolution *in vivo*, real-time images of the human esophagus and so, they can be an important tool for the early diagnosis and prognosis of serious esophageal diseases such as Barrett's, dysplasia and esophageal cancer. Yet, the huge data volumes make manual assessment of the generated information very difficult and the proposed algorithms have not been able to offer effective computer-aided diagnosis. In this study, we compare various machine learning methods for tissue segmentation and classification of esophageal tissue using *in vivo* OCT images. An automated algorithm is proposed able to detect normal tissue from Barrett's Esophagus (BE) and dysplasia. The classification was based on several features extracted from EOCT images, which included intensity-based statistics, group velocity dispersion (GVD) and the average scatterer size (SS) of each A-Scan. The areas of the epithelium were annotated as normal, BE or dysplasia by an expert. The results of various machine learning (ML) classifiers have shown that a neural network based approach provided the best performance, separating BE from dysplasia, for individual A-Scans, with an accuracy of 89%.

1. INTRODUCTION

Barrett's esophagus (BE) is a condition where the normal squamous epithelium of the esophagus transforms to columnar-like, due to gastroesophageal reflux. BE progresses through different stages of dysplasia before developing into esophageal adenocarcinoma thus giving the opportunity for an early detection of the disease, which significantly improves patient prognosis. Patients with confirmed BE undergo periodic endoscopic surveillance with systematic biopsies. However, this procedure suffers from important limitations. Sampling error can lead to misdiagnosis since only a small proportion of the metaplastic BE epithelium is covered by the biopsies (4-6% of the area) [1,2]. Furthermore, the size and morphology of the samples obtained can cause diagnostic uncertainty since it limits inter-observer agreement between pathologists and causes delays in the histopathologic processing [3]. Endoscopic Optical Coherence Tomography (EOCT) systems can acquire cross-sectional images of the microscopic structure of the esophageal layers. By analyzing the microstructure of the epithelium in OCT images, researchers aim to characterize the state of the esophageal tissue, discriminating between normal esophagus and BE with or without dysplasia [4,5]. In the last 20 years, computer-aided diagnosis was exploited in many contexts to provide tissue characterization and classification between malignant and benign regions. Computational methods for the analysis of esophageal OCT images have also been demonstrated [6,7]. In this study, we classify different regions of esophageal OCT images from various patients, utilizing a fully automated algorithm for image segmentation and feature extraction. Several machine learning classifiers were evaluated for accuracy and capability to differentiate normal from abnormal tissues and BE vs. dysplasia from *in vivo* acquired data.

2. METHODOLOGY

A. Image and Data Processing

The OCT images were collected using a swept source EOCT system with a center wavelength of 1300 nm, an axial resolution of 10 μm and an A-Scan rate of 40 kHz. Each catheter rotation produced 2,048 A-Scans, displayed in real-time, and multiple cross-sectional esophageal images were collected as the catheter was manually pulled up from the gastroesophageal junction. *In vivo* data was derived from healthy volunteers and patients with esophageal disease enrolled in a study at Massachusetts General Hospital, approved by the Partner's Internal Review Board (IRB).

This study utilizes OCT esophageal images from ten patients creating a dataset of 320 images. The annotated regions were 461, of which, 170 normal, 118 BE and 173 dysplastic providing a total of 154066 annotated A-Scans. An automated algorithm for tissue segmentation and feature extraction created and utilized to segment the epithelium in order to extract features for image classification. Each image was segmented at three different depths from the top surface of the tissue to

investigate the setting for optimal classification results. The depth of segmentation was 0.4, 0.55, 0.7mm (Fig. 1). The annotated regions were processed to extract features for the training and testing of the ML classifier models.

B. Feature Extraction

The classification of the esophageal tissue was performed using various features extracted from the epithelial portion of the OCT images. These features included:

1. Intensity Statistics

Textural intensity statistics of the OCT images were calculated for the segmented portion of the OCT image. At first, the statistics were calculated for each A-Scan separately for the upper and lower parts of the region's epithelium and then the region was also divided in three parts in order to more closely estimate the intensity differences between the basal layers and the luminal surface of the epithelium. The calculated statistics included the mean, variance, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis, median, and the total, minimum and maximum intensities. In addition, the sliding standard deviation of every statistic an estimate of the variation between the values of adjacent A-Scans, was also included. The result was a total of 36 intensity-based statistics for every A-Scan when the region was divided in half and 54 statistics when the region divided in three parts. The features were calculated separately for the top and bottom layer of the epithelium or alternatively for the top, middle and bottom layers.

2. Group Velocity Dispersion (GVD)

Research has shown that tissue dispersion could be used as a biomarker of early abnormalities to enhance the diagnostic potential of OCT. For this study, we estimated tissue dispersion using the image's speckle, a technique that does not require the presence of distinct reflectors in the imaged tissue and is, therefore, applicable to *in vivo* imaging [8]. This method compares the image speckle from different portions of the segmented area, beginning from the top surface of the epithelium and gradually progressing to the bottom. The GVD is calculated, for each A-Scan, from the speckle width degradation that is proportional to the point spread function (PSF) degradation [9].

3. Scatterer Size

The average scatterer size (nuclei) for each A-Scan of the epithelial layer was estimated applying the bandwidth of the correlation of the derivative (COD) method. The COD is a new spectroscopic metric that extracts information about the modulation of depth-resolved spectra, as predicted by Mie theory, and can be used to calculate the average scatterer size. For each region of the epithelium, the spectrum was extracted using autoregressive spectral estimation. To estimate the scatterer size, the first derivative of the spectrum was calculated followed by its autocorrelation. The lag location of the first minimum of the autocorrelation was used to estimate the scatter size using a function derived from curve fitting of the expected COD calculated from Mie Theory [10].

C. Feature Selection and Classification

Feature selection and optimization was performed in an effort to select the features that result in the best classification results. This process included utilization of a paired t-test and Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA). For the classification, five classifiers were, initially, evaluated: Discriminant Analysis (DA), Naïve-Bayes (NB), Decision Trees (DT), k-nearest neighbor (KNN) and Ensemble of Decision Trees (EDT). The performance of each classifier model was verified using leave-one-out cross-validation and was, subsequently, applied to entire images and volumes. Subsequently, using Python and Keras, different neural networks (NN) were constructed, varying the number of hidden layers and neurons, and each one evaluated on the same dataset. The optimal NN, consisted of 1 input, 1 output and 7 hidden layers with a total of 3,643 trainable parameters. A Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) was used as an activation function with a learning rate of 0,01 as an optimizer. Each neighborhood of the epithelium was classified first as normal vs. abnormal and, subsequently, the abnormal areas were classified as BE vs. Dysplasia [11-14].

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Figure 1 shows an example of an *in vivo* OCT image of the esophagus. In real-time, the image is displayed in the standard Cartesian coordinates (Fig. 1A) which more accurately represent the geometry of the esophagus. However, for processing purposes, the image was retained in polar coordinates (Fig. 1B) so that individual A-Scans could be processed separately. The regions of the images in this dataset were annotated as normal, BE and dysplasia (Fig. 1B, orange boxes). The epithelium

was automatically segmented using automatic thresh-holding and appropriate morphological operations, thus, identifying the top and bottom borders of the epithelium (Fig. 1B, red and green lines). The segmented regions (Fig1C) were used in the machine learning process.

Figure 1. (A) *In vivo* OCT image of the human esophagus in Cartesian coordinates. (B) Same image in polar coordinates with the red and green lines indicating the top and bottom borders of the automatically segmented epithelial region. The orange boxes indicate annotated dysplastic (1), BE (2) and Normal (3) regions. (C) Zoomed regions corresponding (from top to bottom) to the dysplastic BE and normal annotated areas respectively.

Tables I and II presents the results of all classifiers for normal vs abnormal classification (left) and Barrett’s vs. dysplasia (right). The performance of each classification task was verified using a leave-one patient-out-cross validation approach for the same features selected based on t-testing and MANOVA (p -value < 0.05). Mean, variance, median, sum, min and max of the upper and lower parts appeared to be the most significant features along with the GVD and SS. Only one feature of the middle area appeared to be significant (skewness) when the regions divided in three. Normal vs. Abnormal classification was generally more challenging. Since this is a very preliminary study, improving the accuracy of the classifier was the major focus. The neural network (NN) presented the best results (sensitivity of 67%, specificity of 95%, accuracy of 85% and AUC of 0.82) using 0.7mm segmentation depth. For BE vs. Dysplasia classification the neural network (NN) again exhibited the best performance when the epithelium was segmented 0,4mm depth and divided in half with sensitivity of 80%, specificity of 92%, accuracy of 89% and AUC of 0.85.

Table 1. Classification results for Normal vs Abnormal (left) and Barret’s vs Dysplasia (right) using leave-one image out-cross-validation.

Depth [mm]	Region Div.	Classifier	SEN [%]	SPE [%]	ACC [%]	AUC	GM	Depth [mm]	Region Div.	Classifier	SEN [%]	SPE [%]	ACC [%]	AUC	GM
0.4	2	NN	72	92	84	0.78	0.80	0.4	2	NN	80	92	89	0.85	0.84
0.55	2	LDA	76	83	81	0.80	0.79	0.55	2	NN	78	92	86	0.81	0.82
0.7	2	NN	67	95	85	0.82	0.80	0.7	2	LDA	81	79	80	0.80	0.80

4. CONCLUSIONS

Given the results presented in this study, the automated algorithm proposed could be developed to perform in vivo EOCT esophageal tissue segmentation and classification. Using machine learning with a neural network, the algorithm could distinguish Barrett’s esophagus (BE) from Dysplasia with an accuracy of 89%, sensitivity of 80% and specificity of 92% with AUC 0.85. Segmentation depth of 0.4mm to the esophagus epithelial layer appears to be most more appropriate for BE vs. Dysplasia classification and Normal vs. Abnormal. Furthermore, it is clear from the results that the division of the epithelial region in half (top and bottom) during feature extraction led to more effective classification. However, further evaluation is required, with a larger number of images from more patients, to optimize the classifier models and create a system that can be used for effective computer aided diagnosis of EOCT images.

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